

PERCEIVED PARENTAL EXPECTATIONS OF CHILDREN AMONG MIDDLE SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The current research aims to identify the parental expectations perceived by children among middle school students, by answering the following questions: 1- The level of perceived parental expectations (supportive, threatening) for children. 2- Identifying the level of perceived parental expectations (supportive, threatening) among middle school students, according to the variables of sex (male, female). 3- Identifying the level of perceived parental expectations (supportive, threatening) among middle school students, according to the two variables of specialization (literary, scientific).

Keywords: Perceived parental expectations of children _ middle school students

The current research is limited to students of the fifth preparatory schools affiliated to the Directorate of Education of Jalawla, of both sexes (males - females) and specializations (scientific - literary) for the academic year 2022-2023. The research sample included (400) male and female students distributed in (11) schools, of which (5) were for girls, (4) were for boys, and (2) were mixed. To achieve the objectives of the research, the researcher prepared the following scale:

Perceived parental expectations scale.

The validity of the scale was verified by adopting (content validity of both types, virtual validity, logical validity, and constructive validity). The discriminatory power of the items of the scale was calculated. Reliability was calculated using the re-test method, and Cronbach's alpha method for both scales, and the data were treated statistically using the Statistical Bag for Social Sciences (SPSS).

The search results showed the following:

The results of the current research agreed and differed with the results of other previous studies, and this difference is due to the nature of the circumstances and experiences that the sample of this research went through with the samples of other previous studies.

1. The respondents enjoy a high level of perceived (supportive) parental expectations.
2. The males achieved a higher level in perceived parental expectations (supportive/threatening) and in favor of the supportive one.
3. Scientific specialization achieved a higher level in parental expectations (supportive and threatening) and in favor of supportive expectations. In light of the results, the researcher reached a set of recommendations, including:

FIRST - PROBLEM OF THE RESEARCH

The preparatory school stage is considered a pivotal stage in the students' lives. With the student's enrollment in the preparatory stage, children's excellence becomes the primary goal that preoccupies many parents. Success and excellence, and they may ask him makes children find themselves unable to correct or put things back into perspective, and that they are obligated to follow a certain method regardless of the degree of their conviction or approval (Arabiyat, Al-Kharabsheh, 2007: 49).

SECOND - THE IMPORTANCE OF THE RESEARCH

The adolescence stage is a transitional stage in which the individual turns from a child into a mature individual who has a role in life, so the adolescence period is considered as a physical, mental and social transition between the childhood stage and the stage of that result in emotional and social tensions, as these tensions would expose the adolescent to conflicts and internal and external pressures that are reflected on his personality, the family and society (Zahran, 2005: 25:43)

Parental expectations are among the factors influencing children's cognitive and social development. Parental expectations can also backgrounds also have a strong influence on children's academic choices and career choices after secondary school, and they also affect higher expectations of their parents pushes them to make every effort to meet them. Liang indicates that exaggerated and unrealistic. (Jaballah, 2009: 12)

THIRD - RESEARCH OBJECTIVES (AIMS OF THE RESEARCH):

The current research aims to identify:

1. The level of perceived parental expectations (supportive, threatening) for children.
2. Identifying the level of perceived parental expectations (supportive, threatening) among middle school students, according to the variables of sex (male, female).
3. Identifying the level of perceived parental expectations (supportive, threatening) among middle school students, according to the two variables of specialization (literary, scientific).

FOURTH - LIMITS OF THE RESEARCH:

The current research is determined by the study of (parental expectations perceived by children and their relationship to orientation towards the future among middle school students of the General Directorate of Education of Diyala, Department of Jalawla Education, for the morning study for the academic year (2022-2023) for the fifth grade of middle school, of both sexes (male, female) and specialization (scientific and human).

FIFTH: DEFINING THE TERMS

Firstly : . Perceived Parental Expectations

He was known by

1- Jaballah (2009) that they are messages that children receive from parents in order to make efforts to achieve success, and to achieve the best always, and for some it may serve as a supportive motivational motive, and for others there are challenges and pressures, and I have a third category as threats that raise fear and doubt and undermine the individual's self-confidence (2010, Janes)

Theoretical definition of the researcher: They are messages, signals, hints, and desires that children realize from parents in word and deed, and they may be supportive and supportive to sharpen their determination, exert more effort, and achieve a better educational level, or they may be threatening and become a source of pressure that exceeds their capabilities and capabilities and weakens their self-confidence).

Action definition: The score obtained by the respondent by answering the paragraphs of the perceived parental expectations scale, which was prepared by the researcher for this purpose.

Firstly : . Perceived Parental Expectations

Concept of parental expectations

Perceived parental expectations are often overlooked when researching educational issues. Although there have been no extensive reviews published on parental expectations yet, there are a large number of studies that have examined the subject of perceived parental expectations. (3 p.; 2012, Naparstek)

DIMENSIONS OF PARENTAL EXPECTATIONS

First: Supportive parental expectations

Perceived parental expectations, especially the supportive ones, contribute positively to children's academic achievement. Because it development. They appear motivated and uncompromising in carrying out their duties on the one hand, confident and good performance, thanks to support, encouragement, and faith in their abilities and capabilities, and what they excel in in various fields (Oecd, 2013, p:19)

Second: threatening parental expectations

The source of anxiety appears through unrealistic and exaggerated parental expectations and interventions. For starters, the term parental support is sometimes, or encouragement of parents, as it turns into a threat to children, especially with the presence of parental pressure and high expectations.

A height that often exceeds the capabilities of children, especially since children's expectations, plans, and aspirations are variable and emergence of social behavior associated with shyness, hesitation, and low activity and self-efficacy among them. The impact of parental of children only,

but also to aspects related to social and emotional development, such as empathy and positive social behavior (2014, p: 35, Mesurado et al).

Theoretical Explanations Of Perceived Parental Expectations

1- Festinger's cognitive dissonance theory

This theory is based on cognitive dissonance, which is a state of psychological arousal, as this theory explains the link between expectations and performance in many cases, and also explains the relationships between perceived and actual parenting expectations. Seginer and Vermoulis 2002 (Seginer et al) hypothesize the importance of realizing perceived parental expectations on the basis of individuals who set these expectations, and he explains that the implications of this are that children who do not rise To the level achievement according to the desires and expectations of the parents (Vermulst & Seginer, 2002, p: 545).

2- The humanistic theory

Scientist Carl Rogers, the owner of the theory of self, believes that children's tendencies for self-realization work in harmony to satisfy their innate abilities, and this requires positive support from parents and care for them during their various stages of development, by providing directive methods, responses, and demands of others who are important in children's lives and parents is the basis for self-formation, as children need to obtain positive consideration from parents that is characterized by emotional warmth and acceptance (Al-Ani, 99: 2000)

The Second Axis: Previous Studies

- **Studies related to perceived parental expectations**
- **Arabic Studies**

Noura Study (2022)

(The effect of the interaction between personality traits and perceived parental expectations on self-efficacy among high school students)

This study aimed to find out the effect of the interaction between personality traits and perceived parental expectations on self-efficacy among secondary school students. The study sample consisted of (341) male and female students. Secondary stage, and the values of correlation coefficients change between perceived parental expectations and self-efficacy when isolating the effect of personality traits.

Foreign Studies

Perceived parental expectations on the internal psychological adjustment of secondary school students.

The aim was to identify the effect of perceived parental expectations on the internal psychological adjustment of secondary school students. The sample consisted of (383) male and female secondary school students. A self-report tool and a scale of perceived parental developed

relationship with internal psychological adjustment, especially if it reinforced anxiety, depression, and apathy in males and females.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND PROCEDURES

This chapter includes a presentation of the procedures carried out by the researcher in terms of describing the community, selecting the sample, and preparing and building research tools to measure perceived parental expectations. Accurate and scientific descriptions reviewed as follows:

First: the research community: Population of Research

Society means that it is all the individuals who carry the data of the phenomenon that is within reach of the research (Dawood and Abdel-Rahman, 1990: 16), and they are the total group with the phenomenon that the researcher seeks to generalize the results related to the problem to (Odeh and Malkawi, 1987: 159).

The current research community was determined by the students of the preparatory stage of the Directorate of Education of Diyala Governorate - Jalawla Education Department for the academic year (2022-2023 AD), and their number is (5826) male and female students. The researcher obtained this information from the Directorate of Education of Diyala - Department of Education of Jalawla, according to the book Facilitating the Mission (Appendix 1), as in the following table (1):

Table 1: Distribution Of Community Students By School, Gender, And Specialization

Literary fifth			scientific fifth			Total students	School name	T
the total	females	males	the total	females	males			
27	15	12	55	25	30	242	Al-Muhtadi Billah Mixed Secondary School	1
/	/	/	42	42	/	102	Buhaira High School for Girls	2
/	/	/	34	/	34	140	Al-Jabal High School for Boys	3
/	/	/	36	12	22	51	Firefly Mixed High School	4
10	10	/	17	17	/	73	Al Anamil Secondary School for Girls	5
/	/	/	/	/	/	23	Emerald Mixed High School	6
15	/	15	35	/	35	156	Hamrin High School for Boys	7
/	/	/	55	55	/	143	Al Baida Secondary School for Girls	8
/	/	/	75	75	/	285	Sarah High School for Girls	9
24	/	24	82	/	82	three hundred fifty	Martyr Khalil Preparatory School for Boys	10
/	/	/	/	/	/	49	Al-Jinan Evening High School for Girls	11

/	/	/	150	/	150	300	Scientific Approach Preparatory School for Boys	12
/	/	/	96	/	96	551	Jalawla Preparatory School for Boys	13
24	24	/	80	80		340	Hariri High School for Girls	14
45	/	45	43	/	43	194	Barada High School for Boys	15
33	33	/	140	140	/	548	Al-Tayebat Preparatory School for Girls	16
22	/	22	/	/	/	45	Ibn Al-Bitar Mixed Secondary School	17
/	/	/	143	/	143	403	Helwan Preparatory School for Boys	18
2	/	2	2	/	2	184	Agadir Evening High School for Boys	19
/	/	/	11	6	5	42	Mixed secondary school	20
75	/	75	/	/	/	400	Bikhhal preparatory school for boys	21
30	7	23	55	25	30	219	Martyr Hazar Mixed Prep	22
/	/	/	46	21	25	149	Martyr Sirwan Hassan Mixed High School	23
/	/	/	30	30	/	152	Martyr Saman Koija Secondary School for Girls	24
/	/	/	29	29	/	82	Elite High School for Girls	25
27	27	/	193	193	/	587	Scientific High School for Girls	26
8	2	6	/	/	/	16	Modern mixed high school	27
342	118	224	1442	745	697	5826	the total	

Second: Research Sample: Research Sample

In the light of defining the research community and its objectives, the researcher chose his sample in a random, stratified manner according to the variables (gender and specialization). .

Table 2: Distribution Of The Main Research Sample By Gender And Specialization

the total	literary		Practical		schools
	females	males	females	males	
60	12	10	10	28	W / the guided by God mixed
15	---	---	15	---	W/ Al Buhaira for girls
17	---	---	---	17	w/ Mountain for boys
34	---	---	12	22	w/ Firefly Mixed
23	10	---	13	---	w/ fingertips for girls
30	---	---	30	---	W/ Al Baida for girls
45	---	---	45	---	w/ Sarah for girls
50	---	15	---	35	w/ Hamrin for boys
58	---	20	---	38	P / Martyr Khalil for boys
40	---	40	---	---	A / Bekhal for boys

28	28	---	----	---	P / good girls
400	50	85	125	140	the total
	135		265		

Third: - Research Tools: Research Tools

Perceived parental expectations scale (supportive/threatening). In order to build a scale of perceived parental expectations, the researcher had to review studies and literature that dealt with this variable, and he did not find a valid tool that is compatible with his research community and his sample, so he had to build a scale to measure perceived parental expectations according to the following steps:

Drafting of scale paragraphs

After defining the areas of the scale, the researcher formulated the paragraphs, taking into account the following:

Paragraphs should be formulated clearly and in easy, uncomplicated words.

Paragraphs contain one idea.

* Exclude negative articles to avoid confusion in the answer.

After reviewing the definition of perceived parental expectations and its domains, the researcher reached a set of paragraphs that were identified based on the definitions of perceived parental expectations and theories that pertain to this variable, as he was able to formulate paragraphs distributed to the two mentioned domains, as (23) paragraphs were prepared to measure the first domain and (22) A paragraph to measure the second area, and thus the number of paragraphs of the scale became (45) paragraphs, and each paragraph includes five alternatives (it always applies to me, often applies to me, sometimes applies to me, rarely applies to me, does not apply to me).

The validity of the items of the scale

After defining the areas of the scale and formulating its paragraphs, identifying the alternatives to the answer and the method of correcting them, and the degree set for each alternative, the researcher presented the scale of perceived parental expectations in its initial form (Appendix 3) to (20) arbitrators from educational and psychological sciences (see Appendix 4), in order to express their observations On the scale with regard to the validity of the paragraphs, and in order to achieve the objectives of the research, the percentage of the arbitrators' agreement on the paragraphs of the scale was adopted by (90%) or more, and in the light of their opinions or observations, the researcher modified the linguistic wording of some paragraphs, and deleted (12) paragraphs only Of the two fields, by (6) paragraphs from the first field and (6) paragraphs from the second field, the number of the scaled paragraphs became (33) paragraphs. Table (3) shows this.

Table 3: The opinions of the judges about the validity of the scale of perceived parental expectations (supportive and threatening)

the field	paragraph sequence	The number of paragraphs	matchmakers percentage	amendment		delete		chi-square value X ² calculated	square value	verdict
				the number	for percentage	the number	for percentage		Kay X ² - Tabular	
Domain of supportive parental expectations	, 5, 4, 3, 2, 12, 9, 7, 16, 15, 14, 22, 19, 17, 20	14	%100	0	%0	0	%0	20	3,84	Accept
	10, 6, 1	3	%0	19	%95	1	%5	16.2		adjust
	, 13, 11, 8, 23, 21, 18	6	%10	0	%0	18	%90	12.8		delete
and the domain of threatening parental expectations	, 26, 25, 24, 29, 28, 27, 36, 33, 32, 40, 38, 37, 45, 44, 43	15	%100	0	%0	0	%0	20	3,84	Accept
	42	1	%0	18	%90	2	%10	12.8		adjust
	, 34, 31, 30, 41, 39, 35	6	%5	0	%0	19	%95	16.2		delete

Statistical Analysisfor . Items_ _

Prepare analysis statistic for paragraphs more Importance from analysis Logical Because he It is clear Bezel Engagement Paragraph Apparent by the attribute The intended measure it, in when .that analysis statistic more Honestly and reliability (Odeh, 1998: 88)

:psychometric characteristics of the vertebrae Calculating the

Discrimination Power .1of Items The researcher extracted the discriminatory power : the and in order to find , perceived parental expectations scale of the For the items coefficients the two of the method discriminatory power of the items of the scale, the researcher followed : follows as extreme groups

- 1) The scores of the respondents were arranged in their response to the scale of perceived . parental expectations, from the (highest) score to the (lowest) score
- 2) ,of the upper and lower groups were approved to represent the two extreme groups (% 27) as the adoption of (27 %) for the two extreme groups represents the best percentage that can be adopted, because it presents two groups with the maximum possible size and male and (400) differentiation . And because the statistical analysis sample consisted of) Therefore, the number of individuals in the upper and lower groups was female students That is, (108) in the lower group and (108) in the upper male and female students (216 . group
- 3) t -test was used for two independent samples to extract the difference between the upper and lower groups , as shown in Tables (4). All paragraphs of the scale are distinguished because the calculated t- values are greater than the tabular t- value of (1.96) . At a degree . (0.05) of freedom (214) , with a level of significance

Table 4: the results of item recognition scale of perceived parental expectations (supportive/threatening) using the two extreme groups method

indication	calculated t value	standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	the group	threatened paragraph	calculated t value	standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	the group	Paragraph supporting
function	8,153	0,613	4,416	Olya	1	8,214	0,762	4,250	Olya	1
		1,419	3,203	Donia			1,465	2,944	Donia	
function	11,036	0,628	4,416	Olya	2	7,463	0,756	4,268	Olya	2
		1,457	2,731	Donia			1,466	3,083	Donia	
function	8,865	0,669	4,333	Olya	3	11,485	0,687	4,435	Olya	3
		1,484	2,944	Donia			1,417	2,694	Donia	
function	9,207	0,662	4,305	Olya	4	7,271	0,715	4,259	Olya	4
		1,455	2,888	Donia			1,447	3,129	Donia	
function	14,171	0,674	4,351	Olya	5	13,074	0,660	4,351	Olya	5
		1,348	2,296	Donia			1,454	2,342	Donia	
function	9,428	0,657	4,250	Olya	6	9,544	0,657	4,342	Olya	6
		1,517	2,750	Donia			1,372	2,944	Donia	
function	9,745	0,585	4,444	Olya	7	7,932	0,750	4,250	Olya	7
		1,499	2,935	Donia			1,469	2,990	Donia	
function	9,998	0,818	4,240	Olya	8	10,228	0,660	4,351	Olya	8
		1,360	2,713	Donia			1,528	2,713	Donia	
function	16,255	0,553	4,453	Olya	9	10,671	0,672	4,425	Olya	9
		1,340	2,185	Donia			1,397	2,833	Donia	
function	11,594	0,601	4,453	Olya	10	9,801	0,631	4,351	Olya	10
		1,448	2,703	Donia			1,352	2,944	Donia	
function	10,521	0,571	4,481	Olya	11	9,267	0,703	4,361	Olya	11
		1,406	2,944	Donia			1,343	3,009	Donia	
function	9,317	0,657	4,416	Olya	12	8,599	0,682	4,370	Olya	12
		1,459	2,981	Donia			1,438	3,111	Donia	
function	12,113	0,601	4,444	Olya	13	13,173	0,682	4,398	Olya	13
		1,393	2,675	Donia			1,438	2,379	Donia	
function	7,654	0,640	4,398	Olya	14	8,265	0,645	4,351	Olya	14
		1,489	3,203	Donia			1,496	3,055	Donia	
function	10,991	0,571	4,490	Olya	15	10,750	0,679	4,379	Olya	15
		1,421	2,870	Donia			1,510	2,66	Donia	
function	12,165	0,586	4,453	Olya	16	7,869	0,584	4,435	Olya	16
		1,383	2,694	Donia			1,465	3,240	Donia	
function	-----	----	-----	----	---	13,278	0,622	4,379	Olya	17
							1,444	2,370	Donia	

: Internal consistency(paragraph validity): Internal consistency was calculated as follows .2

a. The relationship of the item score to the total score of parental expectations : (supportive/threatening)

" In calculating the veracity of the paragraph, the researcher relied on the Person Correlation " coefficient between the scores of each paragraph and the total score, because the scores of the paragraph are continuous and gradual. Note that the sample of the validity of the paragraphs consists of (400) male and female students in the current research. It was found that all the correlation coefficients are statistically significant when compared to the critical value of the) at the level of significance (0.05) and the degree of freedom (0.098) correlation coefficient of . (398

) Table 5:) Correlation coefficients between the score of each item with the total score perceived supportive parental expectations) and the total score (perceived threatening (parental expectations

Threatening parental expectations		Supportive parental expectations	
Paragraph correlation coefficient component	Paragraph number	Paragraph correlation coefficient component	Paragraph number
0,517	1	0,636	1
0,563	2	0,550	2
0,537	3	0,648	3
0,534	4	0,500	4
0,544	5	0,531	5
0,518	6	0,551	6
0,553	7	0,558	7
0,534	8	0,560	8
0,496	9	0,575	9
0,605	10	0,570	10
0,570	11	0,551	11
0,565	12	0,514	12
0,654	13	0,544	13
0,520	14	0,495	14
0,618	15	0,490	15
0,559	16	0,497	16
		0,516	17

) Psychometric properties For the scalePsychometric features of the Scale : (

First: Validityof the Scale :

For the current scale, two indicators of validity have been extracted, which are virtual validity and :constructive validity. The following is an explanation of how to verify each indicator

1- **_ Virtual honesty_ Validity : (**

(3) The researcher verified this validity by presenting the scale in its initial form Appendix contains a group of experts specialized in educational and psychological sciences To judge the

validity of its paragraphs in measuring what it was prepared to measure, as well as evaluating its instructions and alternatives to answering the paragraphs, and whether the instructions paragraphs, and alternatives to the answer need to be modified , and if there are any suggestions

B- Construct Validity

- Discrimination by finding differences between the two extreme groups
- The relationship of the paragraph score with the total score

Second Scales Reliability

Reliability was calculated using the following retest and Wackeronbach methods

A- method Test - Rete

,For the purpose of extracting stability in this way, the scale was re-applied on a sample of stability which consisted of (60) male and female students, at a rate of (15%) of the research sample , and as Adams indicated ,a time interval of (14) days from the first applicationthat re-application of the scale is for the purpose of To identify its stability, it should not exceed two weeks from the the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated between the degrees of first application, then .for the scale (0.85) the first and second application, and the correlation coefficient reached

B- Cronbach's Alpha equation

Reliability was extracted in this way from the scores of the basic sample questionnaires amounting (0.82) to (400) questionnaires, and using the Cronbach equation, the alpha coefficient reached . according to the common interpreted variance standard, which is a good stability coefficient

Description of the scale in its final form : After the completion of the procedures for building the scale, it became composed in its final form of (33) paragraphs, appendix (5), which is shown :according to table (13) as follows

perceived parental Statistical indicators of the statistical analysis sample of the scale of : expectations (supportive / threatening)

And he has This required the researcher to use the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) .(7/6) Table to extract these statistical indicators, as shown in

Parental (Supportive) Table (6 :) Statistical Indicator Values for the Perceived Expectations Scale

Value	for supporting expectations Statistical indicators	
58,62	mean	Arithmetic mean
57,00	Median	Mediator
53,00	Mode	vein
12,05	std. Deviation	standard deviation
145,25	Variance	variance
0,038	Sleekness	skewness
0,687	Kurtosis	kurtosis
29	Minimum	lower score
83	Maximum	highest score

54,00	Range	Term
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(threatened) Table (7) The values of the statistical indicators of the scale of perceived parental expectations

Value	of threatened expectations Statistical indicators	
55,62	mean	Arithmetic mean
54,50	Median	Mediator
53,00	Mode	vein
11,74	std. Deviation	standard deviation
137,85	Variance	variance
0,102	Sleekness	skewness
0,609	Kurtosis	kurtosis
27	Minimum	lower score
80	Maximum	highest score
53,00	Range	Term

of of the scale Upon observing the values of the aforementioned statistical indicators the table above, the degrees of in perceived parental expectations (supportive / threatening) (supportive / threatening) are close to the shape of their frequency expectations perceived parental distribution from the normal distribution, because the skewness and kurtosis coefficients are close to zero, as the more The skewness coefficient and kurtosis coefficient were close to zero, degrees is close to the shape of the normal distribution, and therefore the scale is accurate in measuring the psychological concept, and the sample is representative of the community, which allows generalizing the results of applying this scale. (Odeh, 1998: 86). Figures (1 and 2) show this

Figure (1) Graph of the statistical analysis sample Perceived (supportive) parental . expectations

Fifth: Statistical means

Most of the statistical methods used in the current research were calculated by the automated) computer programSPSS :are (

1. .t- test : to identify the level of variables in the sample
2. t testT-test for two independent samples to calculate the discriminatory power of the items of the perceived parental expectations scale . It was also used to identify differences in .parental expectations according to the variables of gender and specialization
3. Pearson'sPerson Correlation Coefficient:It was used to find the following
 - Calculation of correlations between item score and total score on the Perceived Parental Expectations scale
4. Cronbach equation for internal consistency was used to extract the stability using the alpha . method for the internal consistency of the research tools
5. equivalent _ t in terms of correlation coefficient

Presentation, interpretation and discussion of the results

This chapter includes a presentation of the results reached based on the objectives that have been identified and the interpretation and discussion of these results according to the theoretical framework and previous studies. The results can be presented as follows

/ objective : to identify the perceived parental expectations of children (supportive threatening) among middle school students

To achieve this goal, the researcher applied the scale of perceived parental expectations of children (supportive / threatening) on a research sample consisting of (400) male and female students. The results of the research showed that the arithmetic mean of the degrees of supportive parental expectations was (67.04) degrees , with a standard deviation of (7.29) degrees. And it was found -that the difference is statistically significant at the level of significance (0.05), as the calculated t value reached (43.97), which is greater than the tabular t- value of (1.96), and with a degree of freedom (399). This means that the research sample has perceived (supportive) parental expectations , and the results of the research showed that the arithmetic mean of the degrees of ,threatened parental expectations is (44.77) degrees, with a standard deviation of (5.56) degrees and for the purpose of knowing the significance of the difference between the arithmetic mean and the hypothetical mean that It reached (48) degrees, the researcher used the t- test for one sample, and it was found that the difference is not statistically significant at the level of significance (0.05), as the calculated t- value reached (-11.60), which is smaller than the tabular t- value of (1.96). , with a degree of freedom (399). This means that the research sample does not .enjoy perceived (threatening) parental expectations, and Table (8) shows this

Table (8) The arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and t -value of the scale of perceived parental expecta children (supportive / threatening)

	indication (0,05)	T value		Hypothetical average	standard deviation	SMA	the sample	variable
		Tabular	calculated					
	function	1,96	43,97	51	7,29	67,04	400	Perceived parental expectations of supportive children
	non function	1,96	-11,60	48	5,56	44,77	400	Perceived parental expectations in threatened offspring

This result indicates that the respondents enjoy perceived (supportive) parental expectations, as these expectations of parents contribute to increasing the academic achievement of their children . Because it creates conditions that encourage positive excellence

objective : to identify statistically significant differences in the perceived parental expectations of children (supportive / threatening) among middle school students According .to the gender variable (male female)

For the purpose of verifying this goal, the researcher took the responses of the research sample of .male and female students on the scale of perceived parental expectations of children (400)

(supportive / threatening) After processing the data statistically, the researcher extracted average scores of supportive parental expectations according to gender (male and female), and it was found that the average score for males was (72.64) with a standard deviation of (3.72), and the average score for females was (59.85) with a standard deviation of (3.44), and the researcher extracted the mean scores of threatened parental expectations according to sex (males and females), and it was found that the mean scores for males were (47.36) with a standard deviation of (4.89), and the mean scores for females were (41.44) with a standard deviation of (4.52) and to find out the differences between males and females, the researcher used the t- test for two independent . (9) samples, and the results were as shown in Table

Schedule (9) The t- test for two independent samples to indicate the difference in the perceived parental expectations of the children according to the gender variable

	indication (0,05)	T value		standard deviation	SMA	the sample	sex	variable
		Tabular	calculated					
	function	1,96	35,17	3,72	72,64	225	males	Perceived parental expectations of children (supportive)
				3,44	59,85	175	females	
	function	1,96	12,40	4,89	47,36	225	males	Perceived parental expectations of children (threatening)
				4,52	41,44	175	females	

It is clear from the above table that there are statistically significant differences in the perceived parental expectations of children (supportive / threatening) according to male and female genders and the male benefit, since the calculated t- value for the supportive (35.17) and the threatening one (12.40) is greater than the tabular t- value of (1.96) And the valid (supportive) expectations are due to the fact that the arithmetic mean of the supportive is higher than the arithmetic mean of the threatened expectations at the significance level (0.05) and the degree of freedom (398) . This result can be explained by the fact that males receive support more than females and perceive this support as encouragement and motivation for themselves to achieve the best. The prestigious that . parents find is one of the most important achievements of children

objective : to identify statistically significant differences in the perceived parental expectations of children (supportive / threatening) among middle school students According .to the variable of specialization (scientific-literary)

For the purpose of verifying this goal, the researcher took the responses of the research sample of male and female students on the scale of the perceived parental expectations of the children (400) (supportive / threatening) and after processing the data statistically, the researcher extracted the average scores of the supportive parental expectations according to the specialization (scientific-literary). The average score for scientific specialization is (67.65) with a standard deviation of and the average score for literary specialization is (65.85) with a standard deviation of ,(7.07) and it turned out that the average score for the scientific specialization was (45.81) with ,(.(7.60) (42.71) a standard deviation of (5.07), and the average score for the literary specialization was ,with a standard deviation of (5.92), and to find out the differences between the two disciplines

the researcher used the t-test for two independent samples The results were as shown in Table (10).(n

Table (10) Test T for two independent samples to indicate the difference in parental expectations perceived by children (supportive / threatening) according to the variable of specialization

indication (0,05)	T value		standard deviation	SMA	the sample	Specialization	variable
	Tabular	calculated					
function	1,96	2,35	7,07	67,65	225	scientific	Perceived parental expectations of children (supportive)
			7,70	65,85	175	literary	
function	1,96	5,44	5,07	45,81	225	scientific	Perceived parental expectations of children (threatening)
			5,92	42,71	175	literary	

It is clear from the above table that there are statistically significant differences in the perceived parental expectations of children (supportive / threatening) According to the scientific and literary specialization and in favor of the scientific specialization, the calculated t- value for the supportive is (2.35) and the threatened one is (5.44), which is greater than the tabular t- value of (1.96) and in favor of the supporting expectations since the arithmetic mean for the supporting one is higher than the arithmetic mean for the threatened expectations at a level of significance (0.05) and a (.398) degree of freedom

And an explanation for this result, as it is not possible to deny the social point of view that is still prevalent in society, which is related to the status and social expectations of each scientific or literary specialization, where the society looks at the scientific specialization holders as more intelligent, superior, and social standing, as parents push their children towards scientific disciplines than In order to obtain social status and the opportunity to work

Conclusions

In light of the researcher's findings through data analysis and discussion, the following can be concluded

1. The respondents have a high level of perceived supportive parental expectations
2. Males achieved a higher level of perceived parental expectations (supportive/threatening) and in favor of supportive
3. Scientific specialization achieved a higher level in parental expectations (supportive and threatening) and in favor of and supportive expectations

Based on the findings of the current research, the researcher : Recommendations :recommends the following

Carrying out courses and meetings to educate parents on how to deal with their children, and -1 to set expectations that are appropriate to their capabilities, potentials, and skills in a realistic . manner that is not exaggerated

Providing a secure family atmosphere in which children realize their parents' expectations in a -2 .positive way that helps them work and achieve

Suggestions

In light of the findings of the current research, the researcher suggests the following

among other perceived parental expectations Conducting a study aimed at revealing the level of -1 .samples, such as university students

1- perceived parental Conducting a study aimed at the nature of the relationship between and some variables, creative thinking, decision-making, and self-disclosure expectations .among middle school students

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